

Correlation between Marital Instability and Academic Performance among Government Secondary School Students in Chikun Local Government Area, Kaduna State

Buba Mahmud¹

Email: mahmudbuba@gmail.com,

Tel: 0703 053 1155

Adamu Jibrilla²

Email: j.adam1438@gmail.com,

Tel: 0703 740 8344

Murtala Muhammad³

Email: muhatala55@gmail.com,

Tel: 0806 901 5927

¹Department of Educational Psychology and Counselling, Faculty of Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria

²Department of Physical Sciences Education, Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola

³Department of Environmental and Life Sciences Education, Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola

Abstract

The study investigated the correlations between marital instability and academic performance among government secondary school students in Chikun Local Government Area, Kaduna State. Two objectives were formulated which lead to two research questions and two null hypotheses that guided this study. The population of this study is made up of 13876 secondary school students in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria. A total of 388 senior secondary school (188 males and 200 females) students were selected using simple random sampling techniques. The study adopted correlational research design. Questionnaire entitled Marital Instability Questionnaire (MIQ) was used for data collection and the reliability coefficients of 0.89 was calculated using Cronbach alpha. Linear regression analysis and independent sample *t* – test were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. The findings of the study revealed that: There is significant relationship between marital instability and students' academic achievement, $r = .718$, $n = 388$, $p < .05$. There is no significant difference in the achievement scores of males and females due to marital instability, t – value = -0.611, $p > 0.05$. It is concluded that students who experience marital instability in their families tend to have different academic outcomes compared to those from stable family backgrounds. It is also concluded that both male and female students appear to be equally affected (or unaffected) by marital instability in terms of their academic performance. It is recommended among others that all marriage stakeholders should put every effort to solve marital crises in order to save the couples from broken home and save the children from adverse consequences of marital instability.

Keywords: Marital Instability, Academic achievement, gender

Introduction

Marriage has existed for as long as there have been humans. It can be considered an institution that has existed ever since man first set foot in the cosmos. Anderson (2015) argued that the institution of marriage is founded on the principle that men and women possess complementary qualities, the biological necessity of both a man and a woman for reproduction, and the recognition that children benefit from the presence of both a mother and a father. According to Ojukwu, Woko and Onuoha (2016) marriage is considered a cultural and universal phenomenon and is usually formalized through a wedding ceremony in many cultures. The husband and wife's traditional roles and responsibilities include cohabitating, limiting their sexual activity to one another, sharing financial resources, and being acknowledged as the children's primary caregivers who prioritize their wellbeing and well-informed education. Formal interactions, however, can only occur in a stable, mutually supportive family setting. Marriage is meant to be stable and eternal, but recent changes in family structures and marital values have redefined marriage institutions in most societies, including Nigeria. This has serious implications for the overall growth and well-being of the family's legitimate children as it becomes more fragile and unstable. With potential repercussions for people's well-being and social dynamics, marital instability—characterized by conflicts, separation, and divorce within marital relationships—has become a common problem across various societies. The institution of marriage is extremely important to culture and society

Correlations between Marital ... (Buba et.al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072009>

everywhere, including Nigeria. However, the dynamics of families have changed as a result of shifting economic, social, and cultural factors, which has increased the incidence of unstable marriages. The phrase "marital instability" refers to a situation where a married couple is having relationship issues. It alludes to a marital crisis or issues between partners that could lead to a marriage ending in divorce, desertion, or separation. According to Katzenback and Smith cited in Oyeromi, Olaolu, Fadokun and Omiyale (2018), marital instability is characterized by arguments in which the couples involved perceive a threat to their needs, interests, or concerns. It is also viewed as a struggle between couples who have divergent needs, ideas, beliefs, values, or goals. A marriage or family according to Alika and Edosa (2012) is structurally stable or unstable. A marriage that is unstable lacks structural integrity due to arguments, fights, separation, or even divorce. These marriages are characterized by frequent arguments, disagreements, and domestic fights between the partners.

Marriage instability has been noted as a current social issue because it has a significant impact on many homes, particularly in Nigerian society. Like the proverbial adage "when two elephants fight, the grass suffers," the situation in most homes is such that even the children have become the burden bearers (Oleabhie & Ighalo, nd). According to Oleabhie and Ighalo (nd), this unpleasant experience frequently leaves them emotionally and psychologically unbalanced with feelings of depression, rage, and even frustration because they are caught between the opposing sides of their parent. Everywhere in the world, marriage is bound by customary rites and taboos. In the majority of cultures, the rituals and ceremonies surrounding marriage are primarily linked to fertility and serve to affirm how crucial marriage is to the survival of an individual or a society. According to Kolo cited in Oyeromi et al (2018), the love of money, freedom, the struggle for power control, poor communication, lack of preparation, or improper diagnosis and treatment of the issue are to blame for the decline in marital vows such as those to love, cherish, and honor. These marital vows have been replaced as a result of this decline by social ills like disaster, poor development, and a lack of appreciation, understanding, companionship, support, attraction, and forgiveness in poor sexual relationships.

The potential impact of marital instability on students' academic performance is one area of particular worry. Academic performance is an important aspect of a student's life because it shapes their educational and future career opportunities. The dynamics of a student's family, including their marital status, have a big impact on how happy and capable of succeeding in school they are. Marital instability can cause a child to experience a variety of stressors, which can affect their emotional and psychological health and possibly have an impact on how engaged and successful they are in school. Earlier studies has shown a link between students' academic performance and marital instability. As an illustration, Oleabhie and Ighalo (nd) found that there is a significant correlation between lack of motivation, depression, and nervous breakdown (caused by marital instability) and undergraduates' academic performance when they studied perceived effects of marital instability on undergraduates' academic performance in Benin city, Edo state. Chindo (2014) looked into the impact of marital issues on students' academic performance. The results showed a significant correlation between marital issues and married students' academic performance. Yongmin and Yuanzhang (2011) found that Children in two-biological-parent families with disruptions experienced slower academic growth than children in two-biological-parent families without disruptions. Simple evidence suggests that marital instability contributes to social, academic, and emotional issues like stress, tension, lack of motivation, and frustration to some extent. The academic performance of a child is undoubtedly negatively impacted by these manifestations (Alika & Edosa, 2012).

According to Fomby and Cherlin (2007) cited in Oyeromi, et al (2018), transitioning from a marital stable to an unstable home is frequently accompanied by declines in children's well-being and academic performance. Children are frequently neglected when marital instability occurs in homes where there are signs like fights and arguments between couples. And such careless neglect on the part of parents in providing the support and guidance required for their children's academic endeavors may result in children's subpar academic performance. Contradictory results have been found regarding the academic achievement of students by gender. According to some studies (Guidubaldo & Perry, 1985; Hetherington, 1985; Kaye, 1989 cited in Oyeromi, et al, 2018), boys in conflicting families have more adjustment issues than girls. According to Oyeromi, et al (2018), some researchers found no difference in the effects of marital instability on boys and girls, while other researchers found more detrimental effects for girls. According to research by Kaye in Oyeromi, Olaolu, Fadokun, and Omiyale (2018), boys and girls perform worse on achievement tests when compared to kids from intact families. Although the potential connection between marital instability and academic performance is becoming more widely acknowledged, there is still a lack of knowledge about the complex interactions between these variables in the particular context of Chikun Local Government Area. There haven't been many thorough investigations into the scope and makeup of this relationship. By conducting a methodical investigation into how marital instability may affect students' academic performance in the local context, this study

Correlations between Marital ... (Buba et.al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072009>

seeks to close this gap. The current study, which is based on the experiences, examines the connection between marital instability and senior secondary students' academic performance in Chikun local government area of Kaduna state, Nigeria.

Marital instability is a pervasive social issue with far-reaching consequences that extend beyond the confines of the marital relationship itself. Among the various facets of society affected by marital instability, the academic performance of students in government secondary schools stands as a critical concern. In Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria, there is a growing concern that marital instability within the households of government secondary school students may be adversely impacting their academic performance. However, a comprehensive understanding of the correlations between marital instability and academic performance in this specific context remains lacking. This study seeks to address the following key issues: To what extent does marital instability within the households of government secondary school students in Chikun Local Government Area influence their academic performance? Are there variations in the academic performance of male and female students from households characterized by varying degrees of marital instability? By exploring these questions, this research aims to provide valuable insights into the complex relationship between marital instability and academic performance among government secondary school students in Chikun Local Government Area, Kaduna State.

Objectives of the Study

This study investigated the correlation between marital instability and senior secondary school student's academic performance in Chukun Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria.

The objectives of the study therefore are as follows:

1. To determine the extent to which marital instability relate to students' Academic Performance in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State.
2. To find out if marital instability has influence on male and female student Academic Performance in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State

Research Question

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the level of relationship between marital instability and students' academic performance in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State?
2. What is the difference in the achievement scores of males and females students due to marital instability in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State?

Null hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant relationship between marital instability and students' academic achievement in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State.
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant difference in the achievement scores of males and females students due to marital instability in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Methodology

The study adopted a correlational design. The population of this study is made up 13876 secondary school students in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State. The sample of this study is 388 (188 male, 200 female) students drawn using Yamane (1967). Simple random sampling technique was used in selecting the subjects. The study used questionnaire entitled Marital Instability Questionnaire (MIQ) for data collection. The questionnaire was duly validated and its reliability coefficient of 0.89 was calculated using Cronbach Alpha method. The terminal examination scores of the students were converted to standard scores and were used as students' academic performance. The data collected were analyzed using regression analysis and independent sample *t* test.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the level of relationship between marital instability and students' academic performance in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State?

Correlations between Marital ... (Buba et.al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072009>

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Level of Relationship between Marital Instability and Students' Academic Performance in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State

S/N	ITEM	Mean	S.D	Remark
1	Children experiencing unstable home environments often display aggressive tendencies.	4.02	1.50	A
2	Offspring of divorced parents may exhibit deviant behavior due to a lack of supervision and behavioral guidance.	3.21	1.53	U
3	Children from divorced or separated families may become wayward, mischievous, unruly, and rebellious.	4.05	1.34	A
4	Kids of divorced parents have a higher susceptibility to child trafficking compared to those raised in intact families.	4.03	1.18	A
5	Offspring of divorced, separated, or abandoned mothers often miss out on quality education, proper socialization, and effective home upbringing.	4.24	1.13	A
6	Children from divorced families are more vulnerable to being exploited in child trafficking compared to those raised in intact households.	3.89	1.39	A
7	Children of divorced parents are more likely to end up working as domestic helpers.	3.80	1.10	A
8	Children of divorced or separated women frequently experience economic hardships.	3.02	1.44	U
Grand Mean		3.78		A

Source: Researcher's Analysis of Field Survey, 2022

Results of analysis in Table 1 show the mean and standard deviation of level of relationship between marital instability and students' academic performance in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State. The grand mean of 3.78 indicate that the respondents agree that there exists some relationship between marital instability and students' academic performance in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Research Question 2

What is the difference in the achievement scores of males and females students due to marital instability in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Students' academic Performance in in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State

Gender	N	Mean	S. D	Mean Difference
M	188	59.32	17.01	1.12
F	200	60.44	18.68	

Source: Researcher's Analysis of Field Survey, 2022

The results in Table 2 show the mean and standard deviation of male and female students in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State. The results shows that the mean academic performance of male and female students are 59.32 (SD = 17.01) and 60.44 (SD = 18.68) respectively. The mean difference in the academic performance of male and female students is 1.12 in favour of female students.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between marital instability and students' academic achievement in Chikun Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Table 3: Summary of Linear Regression Analysis of Relationship between Marital Instability and Academic Achievement

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	R - value	Remark
1	Regression	65.451	1	65.451	410.035	.000 ^b	.718 ^b	H ₀₁ rejected
	Residual	61.614	386	.160				
	Total	127.065	387					

Source: Researcher's Analysis of Field Survey, 2022

Correlations between Marital ... (Buba et.al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072009>

- a. Dependent Variable: Academic Performance
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Marital instability

Analysis in Table 3 shows Linear regression results conducted to test whether any significant relationship exist between marital instability and students' academic performance. The results show that there is significant relationship between marital instability and students' academic performance, $F_{(1, 387)} = 410.035$, $p < 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected since the p – value (0.000) is less than 0.05 level of significance. This means that there is significant relationship between marital instability and students' academic performance.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the achievement scores of males and females Students due to marital instability in Chikun Local Government Area, Kaduna State.

Table 4: Summary of Independent Sample t – test of Difference in the Achievement Scores of Males and Females due to Marital Instability

Gender	N	Mean	S. D	df	t – value	P – value	Remark
M	188	59.32	17.01	386	-0.611	.541	H ₀₂ retained
F	200	60.44	18.68				

Analysis in Table 4 shows the result of t – test carried out to test whether significant difference exist in the achievement scores of male and female students due to marital instability. The results show that there is no significant difference in the achievement scores of males and females due to marital instability, $t_{(386, 0.05)} = -0.611$, $p > 0.05$. This implies that the null hypothesis is retained, that is there is no significant difference in the achievement scores of males and females due to marital instability.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that there is significant relationship between marital instability and students' academic achievement. The finding agrees with that of Clarke, Vandell, McCartney, Owen, and Booth (2000) who found that marital conflicts at homes have negative impact on family characteristics and processes like economic position and parental responsiveness, and are associated with the children's cognitive performance. A similar finding was reported by Sun and Liin(2002) who found out that children in separated or divorced families performed more poorly on tests of cognitive ability at the age of 15 and 24 months than that of children from continuously married and intact families. This situation proves that parental marital conflict or instability affects students' academic achievement.

The finding that there is a significant relationship between marital instability and students' academic achievement holds important implications for both academia and society at large. This result underscores the interconnectedness of family dynamics and educational outcomes, shedding light on the potential impact of marital instability on students' performance in academic settings. The finding highlights the crucial role that the family environment plays in shaping students' academic achievement. Marital instability can introduce emotional turmoil, stress, and disruptions into the lives of students. Such disturbances may affect their ability to concentrate on studies, engage effectively in the learning process, and perform well academically. Marital instability often leads to emotional distress, anxiety, and feelings of insecurity among children. These negative emotions can have a direct impact on cognitive functioning and academic engagement. Students who experience marital instability at home might struggle with maintaining focus, managing their emotions, and coping with the challenges of schoolwork.

The findings also revealed that there is no significant difference in the achievement scores of males and females due to marital instability. The finding is in consonant with that of Frost and Pakiz (1990) whose findings revealed no differences in various effects of marital conflicts between girls and boys. The researchers found no gender difference for self-reported anti-social behavior among adolescents from divorce families although, they found gender differences in other areas (such as truancy and social network). This result is agreement with the argument of Hetherington, 1989 as cited by Lester and Russell (2010) that boys and girls experience some disruption in play situations. In the same vein, the findings is in collaboration with that of Oyeromi, Olaolu, Fadokun and Omiyale (2018) who found that there is no significant difference between male and female students in their experience of family marital conflict.

The finding that there is no significant difference in the achievement scores of males and females due to marital instability is an important result that contributes to our understanding of how gender might interact with the impact of family dynamics on academic performance. The finding suggests that, in the context of marital instability, both male and female

Correlations between Marital ... (Buba et.al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072009>

students are similarly affected in terms of their academic achievement. This highlights a level of gender equality in how family dynamics, specifically marital instability, influence students' performance in educational settings. The absence of a significant difference in achievement scores between genders might indicate that marital instability affects students' academic performance irrespective of their gender. Both male and female students might experience similar emotional and psychological challenges stemming from family disruptions, which in turn impact their ability to focus, study effectively, and engage in their education.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that students who experience marital instability in their families tend to have different academic outcomes compared to those from stable family backgrounds. It is also concluded that both male and female students appear to be equally affected (or unaffected) by marital instability in terms of their academic performance.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. All marriage stakeholders should put every effort solve marital crises in order to save the couples from broken home and save the children from adverse consequences of marital instability.
2. Government should develop support programs and interventions that do not differentiate between male and female students but are designed to help all students cope with the potential challenges arising from marital instability.

Acknowledgements

We would like to extend our heartfelt gratitude to the Principals of senior secondary schools in Chikun Local Government Area (LGA) for their invaluable support and cooperation throughout the duration of our research. We would also like to express our sincere appreciation to the students of senior secondary schools in Chikun LGA who willingly participated in our research.

References

- Alika, H.I. & Edosa, O.S. (2012). Relationship between broken homes and academic achievement of secondary school students in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State, Nigeria. *College Student Journal*, 46(2), 11 – 29.
- Anderson, R. (2015). *Fields of training: Manual European Centre for the Development of Vocational training*. Thessaloniki
- Chindo, M. G. (2014). *Influence of marital conflicts on academic performance of married students in state owned tertiary institutions of Kaduna state*. Unpublished M. Ed Thesis, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria.
- Clarke- Stewart, K. A., Vandell, D. L., McCartney, K., Owen, M. T., & Booth, C. (2000). Effects of parental separation and divorce on very young children. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 14(2), 304-326.
- Ersanlı, K., & Kalkan, M. (2008). *Evlilikilişkilerinigeliştirme- KuramveUygulama*[Improvement of marriage relations - Theory and Practice]. Ankara, Turkey: Nobel Yayıncılık.
- Fomby, P., & Cherlin, A. J. (2007). The Family Instability and the Child Well-being. *Psychological Review*. 72(2), 181-204.
- Frost, S. T. & Pakiz, K. J (1990). Children from disrupted family reported truancy in higher proportions. *Journal of divorce* 17(82), 731-742.
- Katzenback, J. R.& Smith, D. K. (1992). *The wisdom of teams: creating the high-performance organization*. Harvard Business School: Boston.
- Kaye, S. H. (1989). The impact of divorce on students' academic performance. *Journal of divorce*, 12 (2/3) 283–299.
- Kolo, F.D. (2011). *Lead Paper Presented at Home Economics Council of Nigeria Conference*, May 14 2011 Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.
- Lester, S. & Russell, W. (2010). *Children right to play: An examination of the importance of play in the lives of children worldwide*. Working Paper No. 57. The Hague, The Netherlands: Bernard van Leer Foundation.
- Ojukwu, M.O., Woko, S. I. & Onuoha, R.C. (2016). Impact of Educational Attainment on Marital Stability among Married Persons in Imo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education & Literacy Studies*, 4(3), 88 – 96.
- Oleabhielle, E. J. & Ighalo, P. O. (nd). *Perceived consequences of marital instability on the academic performance of undergraduates in Benin city, Edo State*.
- Oyeromi, S.O., Olaolu, F.A., Fadokun, J.B., & Omiyale, G.T. (2018). Effects of Marital Stability and Divorce on the Academic Performance of Adolescent Students' in Senior Secondary Schools in Ogun State, Nigeria. *Greener Journal of Educational Research*, 8(4), 094-100, <http://doi.org/10.15580/GJER.2018.4.071217085>.

Correlations between Marital ... (Buba et.al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10072009>

- Sun, Y., & Liin, Y. (2002). Children's well-being during parents' marital disruption process: Apooled time-series analysis. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 64, 472-488.
- Yongmin, M. & Yuanzhang, L. (2011). The various findings show that the proportion of adolescent. *Psychological Review*, 33(4) 552-563.